

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

A Review, Phyto-Electricity: Generation of Electricity From (Solanum Tuberosum)

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Abstract

Phyto-electricity is the process of generating or getting energy from green plants by using them as an electrolyte and inserting different metal plates in them to act as electrode in other to tap into the energy embedded in them and converting them to useful electric energy. Nowadays generating electricity from green plant has become very popular, but phyto-electric power generation has not been able to supply substantial energy to humans and this is due to the low electron in the plants used to generate electricity. In past research people have used trees to generate electricity. The phyto-electric power system works on same principle as the battery. In this design potato will be used as a source of power or as the green plant the battery which is filled with electrolytes, the more the electrolyte the higher the voltage that is readily available to be used, in other to be able to savor the power from the potato two dissimilar metals was used and the metals used were iron and zinc. After completing all of the paper design and analysis, the project was implemented, built, and tested to guarantee that it functioned properly. Electricity was generated and it was used to power a LED, the total resistance of the wire is 1Ω , there is also voltage loss across each node. This project was a success, but more research still needs to be done. And this project is a prove that energy are available in our surroundings, they are just needed to be investigated and further researched and there are more areas of energy and technology development that are yet to be addressed that are various problems faced by man in his day to day activities.

Keywords: Electricity; Phyto-electricity; Electrolytes; Power generation; Phyto; Plants

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1. Introduction

A lot has been said about electricity generation in the world. Electricity generation is mainly about converting other forms of energy into electric energy. Research on electricity started in the early 1800s by Michael Faraday and his method is still used till date. Electricity generation for commercial use started in the late 1800s.

Over the years Nikola Tesla and Thomas Edison are part of the scientists that have made significant contributions in electricity generation. One of the main contributions of Nikola Tesla is the Alternating Current which is the best for distribution of electricity in households. Thomas Edison, one of America greatest inventors contributed the Direct Current which is used to power most electrical appliances in the world. An event happened in the course of history called the "The War of Currents" it was a debate between

the Alternating Current and the Direct Current, argument on which is better, grew during the 1890s.

Over the years both movement of currents have been used in different areas in terms of electricity. Alternating Current is mainly used in electricity distribution in households, offices and so on while Direct Current powers most appliances. These appliances have a converter or rectifier that converts Alternating Current to Direct Current since they operate using Direct Current. Power generation cannot be overemphasized, Electricity determines the civilization of a country, Electricity is important for the development of any country. Most of the developing countries and low-income countries in the world suffer from lack of sufficient power. Countries' economies are dependent on electricity. The world is dependent on electricity now, most of the things we do in our day-to-day